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Abstract:

This milestone report details the comprehensive 3D mechanical model of the Cooling Cell, a critical component for the Muon Collider. It traces the evolution of the design from its initial conceptualization to a fully integrated engineering model, addressing key challenges in magnet-RF-absorber integration, mechanical architecture, and thermal/vacuum boundary development. The introduction of the Inter-Cell Cryostat and the adoption of pillow-seal vacuum interfaces proved pivotal in achieving a compact, robust, and remotely compatible design, confirming the successful achievement of Milestone MS21.

MuCol Consortium, 2025

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Executive summary

This document provides a concise account of the design evolution and engineering achievements culminating in Milestone MS21. It details the progression of the Cooling Cell design from the conceptual B5/S5-like configuration presented in Deliverable D8.1 to a fully integrated 3D engineering model.

Between early 2024 and late 2025, the WP8 team conducted a systematic design effort, encompassing multiple iterations of magnet-RF-absorber integration, mechanical architecture definition, and thermal/vacuum boundary development. A key turning point was the successful implementation of the Inter-Cell Cryostat presented at the Fermilab Demonstrator workshop, which resolved crucial integration conflicts and enabled a compact and feasible layout. This new architecture facilitates the complete closure of magnetic forces within the cold mass (with the exception of the cooling section's extremities), thereby decoupling the cryogenic magnet structure from the room-temperature RF cavity, absorber systems, and inter-cell connections.

Concurrently, the strategy for remote-handling compatible vacuum connections evolved from early SMA seal concepts to custom-designed, high-TRL pillow-seal technology. This solution offers a reliable and compact interface, compatible with the highly constrained space inside the magnet bore and between RF cavities. These developments, in conjunction with the MAG2.4 HTS coil design, an updated RF mechanical structure, and LiH absorber integration, constitute the foundation of the completed 3D model, which was validated at the Milan Demonstrator workshop (5–6 November 2025). Consequently, the objective of this milestone is deemed successfully attained.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Cooling Cell constitutes a fundamental building block in the rectilinear 6D cooling lattice for a future Muon Collider [1,2]. Its purpose is to reduce the transverse and longitudinal emittance of the muon beam through a sequence of absorbers, RF accelerating structures, and focusing solenoids. The efficient integration of all these components within a compact cryo-mechanical environment is essential for achieving the performance predicted by beam dynamics simulations.

Following Deliverable D8.1, which established the conceptual layout and selected a B5-type cooling cell for engineering studies, Milestone MS21 endeavours to deliver the first complete 3D mechanical model of such a cell. This model integrates constraints and requirements originating from MuCol-WP4 (Muon Production and Cooling), MuCol-WP6 (RF systems), MuCol-WP7 (Magnet systems), window engineering and cryogenics. The resulting design serves as the reference configuration for the Muon Cooling Demonstrator [3,4,5] being pursued at CERN within the International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC).

This document provides a technical account of the design evolution, delineating how initial integration challenges—related to magnetic forces, heat loads, waveguide routing, access limitations, and vacuum interfaces—were resolved through the introduction of new design concepts such as the Inter-Cell Cryostat and pillow-seal vacuum interfaces. The resulting 3D model consequently forms the backbone of the demonstrator design and signifies the achievement of MS21.

2. COOLING CELL DESIGN OVERVIEW

The Cooling Cell serves as the fundamental building block of the rectilinear 6D cooling lattice. Within the B5-like configuration selected for the Demonstrator, each cell comprises:

- a low-Z absorber to reduce both transverse and longitudinal momentum through ionization cooling,
- a 3-cell RF accelerating structure to restore longitudinal momentum,
- a high-field HTS solenoid pair to provide high gradient in large apertures,
- a complete mechanical support and alignment system, and
- warm-cold interfaces compatible with remote handling.

The MS21 model represents the initial comprehensive incorporation of all these elements into a true engineering configuration, respecting both lattice optics constraints and realistic mechanical/thermal boundaries. The resulting assembly demonstrates the feasibility of a compact (1000 mm) cooling cell featuring a 3 RF cells structure, somewhat longer than the ultra-compact 800 mm long cell preconized in [6,7] shown in Fig. 1. The result was achieved through the organization of subsystems around the Inter-Cell Cryostat architecture.

Fig. 1. From MuCol D8.1 report: schematic of a Cooling Cell (for reference parameters for RF, Magnets and absorber see D8.1 report [7]). The target was a cooling cell of 800 mm length.

3. EVOLUTION OF THE COOLING CELL CONFIGURATION: THE INTER-CELL CRYOSTAT

The initial designs endeavored to place the two solenoids completely outside the RF envelope. However, as presented at the Fermilab workshop [4], these solutions yielded very high peak magnetic fields exceeding 25 T, unacceptable e.m. forces among coils more than 50 MN, and excessive heat loads. These figures, **unacceptably high**, were obtained with an overall cell length above 990 mm and **with a field reduced by 25%** with respect to the requested one (7 T peak on the beam axis) [7], see Fig. 2, that made the design actually not compatible with the focusing requirements by beam dynamics.

Fig. 2. (from Fermilab workshop): first cell design with RF Cavity+power coupler assembly which is independent of Magnet cell assembly

The above features made the first design of Fig.2 incompatible with the cooling lattice requirements.

During the Fermilab workshop, the concept of the ‘Inter-Cell Cryostat’ was introduced. This innovation permits the closure of magnetic forces within a cold, robust mechanical structure, while the RF and absorber systems are maintained at room temperature.

The electromagnetic (e-m) forces exerted on the SC coils are reacted internally within the cold mass, thus obviating the need for transmission to warm supports. This eliminates several critical constraints, including:

- A substantial reduction in magnetic forces transmitted to the warm structure.
- A consequent reduction in heat load by approximately a factor of 50 compared to the previous solution.
- The internal reaction of forces by adjacent elements, which contributes to reducing stress and torques.

- Independent assembly of RF and absorber systems.
- Viable routing of waveguides and couplers.
- Enough space for remote handling cell-to-cell beam pipe connection.
- Acceptable total cell length (1000 mm), mainly driven by solenoid size and by the space for the RF power wave guide.
- Improved maintainability.

In summary, this approach reduces the cold mass volume, facilitates proper routing of the RF waveguide, and resolves the coupling issues between magnets and RF structures. The Inter-Cell Cryostat is now regarded as the backbone of the design. However, it is important to acknowledge a specific disadvantage of this solution:

- The right half-cell coils of the $(n-1)$ th cooling cell are strongly mechanically coupled with the left half-cell of the n th cooling cell.
- In a string or series of cooling cells, the electromagnetic (e.m.) forces on the first and last half-cell solenoids must still be reacted by a warm structure. This latter drawback is less significant for the final MC Cooling Section, with cooling stages 50 to 100 m long but becomes critical for the initial cells and for a limited number of cells.

Fig. 3 schematic showing the concept of the inter-cell cryostat.

In addition to the Inter-Cell Cryostat, the concept of designing the cell from a global module perspective, e.g., 5 or 6 cells mounted on a robust girder was also introduced, as suggested by the Integration Review [8]. The interference and clearance were inferred by the study for the RFMFTF, the split-coil test facility for the RF studies and tests designed by INFN and Univ. of Milan [9]. The MS21 design represents the first complete engineering implementation of this new architecture.

Fig. 4. The intercell cryostat applied to the cell design (solenoidal coil configuration in the picture is the MAG2.3, now superseded by MAG2.4; remote handling and RF design are not updated, too, in this sketch).

4. MAGNET SYSTEM: MAG2.4

The MAG2.4 configuration, developed with multi-objective optimisation, uses HTS REBCO non-insulated coils operating at 20 K. The design satisfies field requirements, mechanical integrity, and thermal constraints. Charging transient analyses and quench studies indicate feasible operation, though some quench scenarios still require optimisation, which will continue in WP7.

The MAG2.4 solenoid configuration emerges from a multi-objective optimisation, balancing the following requirements while satisfying the cell spatial constraints:

- target field along the axis,
- current margin limits,
- conductor volume,
- peak magnetic field,
- cooling cell length,
- stored energy
- coil axial forces,
- force symmetry,
- torque minimization,
- hotspot temperature limit in case of quench.

HTS REBCO was selected for its ability to operate at 20 K with a wide temperature margin. This approach reduces cryogenic power consumption by an order of magnitude relative to LTS magnets. Mechanical FEA confirms acceptable stresses in normal operation, while charging simulations show that the magnets can be powered using a 4-hour ramp [10,11]. Quench simulations with active

protection (induction heaters) limit unbalanced forces to manageable levels. MAG2.4 has been therefore adopted as the reference for MS21 and fully integrated into the 3D geometry.

Optimal Solution Main Parameters	Coil 1	Coil 2	
		Total	
Coil current (A)	761.2		1193
Number of turns (-)	485		456
Number of pancakes (-)	11		3
Coil radius (mm)	285		185
Axial position (mm)	146		56
SS spacers width (mm)	7.9		13.7
Axial Force (Total) (MN)	-4.6	7.1	11.7
Temperature Margin (K)	21		13
Energy Density (MJ/m3)	152		147
Hotspot Temperature (K)	142		144
Total HTS tape length (km)	43.3	50.9	7.60

Thermal Design Parameters	Value
Number of cryocoolers (-)	4
Radiation power on the thermal shield (W)	63
Heat load on gravity supports (W)	15
Static heat loads on coils (W)	20
Peak power on both coils at charging (W)	127
Max temperature increase Coil 1 / Coil 2 (K)	32 22
Total charging time (h)	6
Cooldown time: 77 K – 20 K (h)	~ 15

Fig.5. Main parameters of the solenoidal coil configuration MAG2.4, selected for the integration. (Courtesy of G. Scarantino and M. Statera, MuCol WP7)

5. RF STRUCTURE INTEGRATION

A 3-cell, 704 MHz RF structure with thin metallic windows has been designed by WP6, [12], to be placed at each IRIS to reduce power requirement while increasing the effective gradient. The RF structure with its waveguide (WG) power feeder and cooling pipes have been integrated into the 3D Model. Aluminium windows (**150 μm , 60 mm radius**) were selected for the Demonstrator primarily due to their manufacturing feasibility and safety considerations while still satisfying the electromagnetic performance requirements for the Demonstrator. The 3-cell, 704 MHz copper cavity RF system features a number of small channels (grooves) connecting the volume of the cavity to the volume of the absorber chamber, bypassing the thin metallic foil. These channels allows the absorber chamber to be pumped via the RF cavity structure, thus avoiding dangerous differential pressure that might be generated in case the two volumes (RF cavity and absorber chamber) would be kept fully separated. The Inter-Cell Cryostat enables direct integration of power couplers and waveguides,

thereby circumventing previous mechanical conflicts and ensuring acceptable cooling (the cavity walls are water-cooled) to avoid thermal gradients.

Key integration challenges addressed included:

- Routing of the waveguide in the restricted space between the cryostat and support structure,
- Placement of power couplers and tuners,
- Mechanical fixation and stress tolerance of thin windows,
- Channels to connect the two vacuum volumes (absorber chamber and cavity)
- Ensuring uniform cooling via multiple external circuits, and
- Managing thermal expansion across warm-cold boundaries.

The Inter-Cell Cryostat proved instrumental in resolving these conflicts: RF and absorber systems are assembled independently at room temperature, thereby enabling access previously unattainable in earlier designs.

Fig. 6. Various views of the 704 MHz 3-cell RF structure with its powering waveguide for the B5-like Cooling Demonstrator Cell. (Courtesy of D. Giove, MuCol -WP6).

6. ABSORBER SYSTEM

The LiH absorber, supported by a dedicated holder with pillow-seal vacuum interfaces, has been integrated into the 3D model. While LiH introduces a slight reduction in performance compared to liquid hydrogen, it is the sole material compatible with the engineering constraints of the Demonstrator. A LiH absorber was selected for the first demonstrator primarily considering its practical safety and manufacturability and based on the positive experience at MICE experiment [13]. Liquid hydrogen, while offering superior cooling performance, necessitates complex handling, safety systems, and risk studies that are incompatible with the early integration and timeline of the Demonstrator. LiH provides:

- Stable solid-phase operation,
- Manageable machining and tolerances, and
- Predictable thermal and mechanical behavior under beam heating.

The absorber is supported by an adjustable mount and integrates pillow-seal based vacuum interfaces, which are compatible with remote handling. This system can also accommodate wedge geometries if dispersion optimization is required in future variants.

Fig.7: LiH as used in MICE (Courtesy of J. C. Pereira Lopes, WP8)

7. REMOTE-HANDLING CONNECTIONS: FROM SMA TO PILLOW SEAL

The vacuum interface between the RF cavity and the absorber line necessitates remote assembly within the highly constrained warm bore of the solenoid structure. Initially, the WP8 team evaluated Shape-Memory Alloy (SMA) seals due to their inherent compactness and self-actuating properties. SMA seals offered several potential advantages, including: the absence of mechanical actuators inside the solenoid, a small radial footprint, and self-equilibrated sealing pressure. However, this option presented several limitations:

- SMA rings are not commercially available at the required diameter (~120–160 mm).
- Activation necessitates cooling to -40°C , a process that is challenging within the constrained space of the cooling cell.
- Alignment tolerances and surface-finish requirements are demanding.
- The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) remains low (3–4), with limited operational experience.
- Replacement scenarios for maintenance are currently unclear.

Given these constraints, automated collar mechanisms—well established at SPS, J-PARC, and Belle-II—were reconsidered. However, despite their high reliability and TRL, their radial envelope significantly exceeded the feasible limits for the Cooling Cell.

WP8 subsequently adopted pillow-seal technology. These seals consist of two metal membranes with a pressurizable interspace, enabling metal-to-metal contact under controlled compression. Their advantages include:

- High TRL (8), demonstrated in harsh radiation environments.
- Compact radial integration compatible with bore constraints (only if custom-designed).
- Tolerance to moderate misalignments.
- Simpler assembly and remote operation.
- Availability of elastomer-based O-ring variants, which reduce surface-finish demands.

The custom *ad hoc* design allowed both to cope with the space constraint and to drastically reduce the differential pressure needed to compress the O-ring. This last point is critical to avoid generating huge axial net forces due to differential pressure: nevertheless, the axial forces remain of the order of 0.5 tons. Concerns regarding reliance on compressed air can be mitigated by integrating redundant supply systems, buffer tanks, check valves, and optional mechanical locks to secure the seal after inflation, even if the very low differential pressure (~ 100 mbar are required in our design) reduce the concerns. Prototype development is planned to validate sealing behavior and integration. The pillow-seal solution, see Fig. 8, is now established as the baseline and is fully reflected in the MS21 model.

Fig. 8. Pillow seal layout.

8. MECHANICAL AND THERMAL ARCHITECTURE

The magnet structure utilizes a 316LN shell with optimized GFRE support posts. Heat loads to 20 K and 60 K levels have been roughly evaluated using the study conducted for the RFMFTF project, resulting in values compatible with cryocooler-based or He-gas-based cooling systems. More precise studies with definitive figures will be conducted and incorporated into the final deliverable (complete design of the Cooling Cell). The 15 mm radial gap between the RF and cryostat, and the

45 mm cold-warm clearance, have been preserved in the layout. The cold mass is supported by GFRE feet, tuned for stiffness versus heat conduction. The design limits thermal loads to approximately:

- 5 W at 20 K, and
- 100 W at 60 K,

These are compatible with cryocooler-based or forced helium cooling. Warm-cold boundaries adhere to the mandatory 40 mm clearance derived from RFMFTF requirements. Finite-element analysis confirms that stresses remain within material limits under both balanced and 10% unbalanced load conditions. The RF structure and absorber remain entirely at room temperature, connected solely via vacuum and mechanical interfaces, thereby providing clear assembly pathways and reduced integration risk.

A global evaluation of all thermal loads (magnets, support, radiation and current leads) will be carried out in the next months and will be reported in the final design D8.2 report.

9. VERIFICATION OF MILESTONE ACHIEVEMENT

The MS21 design now includes all major components:

- HTS magnet pairs (MAG2.4),
- RF cavities with windows and waveguide routing,
- LiH absorber assembly,
- cryostat architecture,
- warm–cold boundaries,
- mechanical supports,
- remote-handling interfaces (pillow seals).

All elements are present in the 3D geometry and have been reviewed in the IMCC Cooling Demonstrator workshop (Milan, 5–6 November 2025). A number of images are reported in Figures 9 to 11, while a complete set of technical drawings are placed in the EDMS repository: <https://edms.cern.ch/document/3388766/1>.

Although further optimisation is expected, the engineering completeness, of the MS21 model fully satisfies the milestone objective.

10. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The expanded 3D engineering model delivered for MS21 successfully integrates all primary components of the B5-like Cooling Cell: high-field HTS solenoids, a 3-cell 704 MHz RF cavity, a LiH absorber assembly, cryostat with thermal shield, support structures, waveguide routing, and vacuum interfaces. The introduction of the Inter-Cell Cryostat provided a decisive solution to early challenges, enabling a compact and feasible architecture that satisfies mechanical and electromagnetic constraints.

The transition from SMA-based seals to pillow-seal technology further improved the design's robustness and remote-handling compatibility. While optimisation continue, the design maturity achieved clearly fulfils the MS21 objective. The model was validated at the WP8 session in the IMCC

Cooling Demonstrator meeting in Milan (5–7 November 2025), confirming that the milestone is complete and providing a sound basis for the next phases of development.

The WP8 team, in collaboration with WP4, WP6, and WP7, will now proceed with a detailed engineering design for the B5-like cell for the Demonstrator. This will involve accurate mechanical and thermal calculations, addressing the cell's start/end conditions (ensuring unbalanced forces are kept at room temperature). Subsequently, a fault scenario analysis and a detailed assembly and maintenance procedure will be conducted. Finally, the **last deliverable of WP8, D8.2 report [Final report on cooling cell design]**, will document the complete design of the cooling cell envisioned for the Demonstrator.

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Fig. 9. A single inter-cell cryostat unit (half and half cell) with quotes. (Courtesy of M. Castoldi, WP8)

Fig.10. 5-cell module on the girder, with a X-section of one and half-cell with quotes. (Courtesy of M. Castoldi, WP8).

Fig. 11. Rendering of a 5 cell-module in a technical building. (Courtesy of M. Castoldi, WP8).